

NMIMR-IRB PARENTAL CONSENT FORM

Title: Surveillance of Pathogens associated with Diarrhea Outbreaks in Ghana: Detection and Molecular Characterization of Diarrhea causing Parasites

Principal Investigator: Dr. Irene Ayi

Address: Department of Parasitology, Noguchi Memorial Institute for Medical Research, University of Ghana, Tel.: +233-243670493; E-mail: IAyi@noguchi.ug.edu.gh; Ayiirene224@gmail.com

General Information about Research

Dear parent/guardian, this consent form contains information about the above titled study. We are carrying out this study in order to identify and understand the parasitic agents such as worms and others that we do not see with the naked eyes that cause diarrhea in Ghanaian children. Understanding which parasites are responsible for diarrhea in children and their characteristics will help with provision of proper prevention and management of diarrhoea.

We will need stool samples from children with diarrhoea reporting to hospital. If you agree for your child to participate in this study, we shall collect his/her stool sample and test in our laboratory for parasitic germs. You will answer a few questions about your child and his/her illness.

Possible Risks and Discomforts

Only stool samples passed by your child will be collected. This will not cause any harm to your child. The necessary precautions will be taken at all times to ensure the safety of your child.

Possible Benefits

There are no direct benefits to your child from this study. His/her participation may however help us to better understand which parasitic agents are causing diarrhea in Ghanaian children. This information may benefit the community as it will provide useful information to the health workers on how to offer better treatment to your child and other diarrhoea patients.

Confidentiality

All information will be protected and kept confidential. Your child will not be named in any report or publication. However, some key members of the research team staff including study physician, laboratory and data analysts may sometimes look at your child's records. Your child's test results may also be made available to your child's doctor upon request.

Compensation

Your child will not be paid for participation in this study but will receive a token (biscuits and a tin of ideal milk) for the time he/she spends to participate in this study. This token will be given to him/her after you, the parent/guardian, have consented for your child to be part of the study and the stool samples have been collected.

Voluntary Participation and Right to Leave the Research

Your child's participation in the study is voluntary and you are free to decide not to continue to participate in the study at any point in time, without any negative consequences on you or your child.

Contacts for Additional Information

If you ever have any questions about the research study or study-related problems, you may contact Dr. Irene Ayi (0243670493) or Dr. William Anyan (0268012634) of the Noguchi Memorial Institute for Medical Research (Office Tel: 0302-501178 or 0302-501179).

Your rights as a Participant

This research has been reviewed and approved by the Institutional Review Board of Noguchi Memorial Institute for Medical Research (NMIMR-IRB). If you have any questions about your child's rights as a research participant you can contact the IRB Office between the hours of 8am-5pm through the landline 0302916438 or email addresses: nirb@noguchi.ug.edu.gh or HBaidoo@noguchi.ug.edu.gh.

VOLUNTEER AGREEMENT

The above document describing the benefits, risks and procedures for the research titled “*Surveillance of Pathogens associated with Diarrhea Outbreaks in Ghana: Detection and Molecular Characterization of Diarrhea causing Parasites*” has been read and explained to me. I have been given an opportunity to have any questions about the research answered to my satisfaction. I agree for my child to participate as a volunteer.

Date

Name and signature or mark of parent/guardian

If volunteers cannot read the form themselves, a witness must sign here:

I was present while the benefits, risks and procedures were read to the volunteer’s parent/guardian. All questions were answered and the parent/guardian has agreed to let his/her child take part in the research.

Date

Name and signature of witness

I certify that the nature and purpose, the potential benefits, and possible risks associated with participating in this research have been explained to the above individual.

Date

Name Signature of Person Who Obtained Consent